

Experimental

4,6-Diacetylresorcinol (1) was prepared by the reaction of acetic anhydride and resorcinol in the presence of $ZnCl_2 \cdot 1$ on condensation with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide³ gave 2',4'-dihydroxy-5'-(4-methoxy)cinnamoyl-4-methoxychalcone (2). Its isomer 3 was prepared by similar condensation with *O*-methoxybenzaldehyde.

(2)

2',4'-Dihydroxy-5'-(4-methoxy)cinnamoyl-4-methoxychalcone (2): 1 (1 g) was mixed with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (2 ml) in ethanol (20 ml) and aqueous potassium hydroxide (10 g in 10 ml of water) and allowed to stand for 24 h. The yellow solid that resulted on acidification with 1:1 hydrochloric acid was filtered and recrystallised from acetone-ethanol as yellow needles (1.5 g), m.p. 184-86°, $C_{26}H_{22}O_6$; ν_{max} (MeOH) 241, 288, 354 and 387 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3600-3400 (br), 3060, 2980, 2900, 1650, 1600, 1540, 1230, 1060, 850 and 740 cm^{-1} ; δ (60MHz, $CDCl_3$) 4.0 (6H, s, OMe), 8.65 (1H, s, C_{α} -H), 6.65 (1H, s, C_{β} -H), 8.1 (2H, d, C_{β} -H) and 7.1-7.85 (10H, m, 8Ar-H + 2 C_{α} -H); m/z (%) 430 (M^+ , 50.5), 399 (3.87), 296 (12.34), 281 (5.38), 268 (9.47), 161 (12.83), 134 (100), 121 (60.74), 108 (7.18) and 91 (15.53).

2',4'-Dihydroxy-5'-(2-methoxy)cinnamoyl-2-methoxychalcone (3): A similar reaction of 1 with *O*-methoxybenzaldehyde gave a light orange coloured product which was recrystallised from acetone-ethanol as orange coloured needles (1.5 g), m.p. 187-9°, $C_{26}H_{22}O_6$; ν_{max} (MeOH) 252, 312, 355 and 384 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3520 (br), 3040, 2980, 2900, 1670, 1590, 1520, 1500, 1220, 1060, 840 and 750 cm^{-1} ; δ (60MHz, $CDCl_3$) 4.0 (6H, s, OMe), 8.8 (1H, s, C_{α} -H), 6.65 (1H, s, C_{β} -H), 8.4 (2H, d, C_{β} -H), and 7.1-8.0 (10H, m, 8Ar-H + 2 C_{α} -H); m/z (%) 430 (M^+ , 72.18), 399 (100), 323 (12.66), 296 (12.09), 281 (12.8), 265 (68.1), 189 (13.3), 163 (45.8), 134 (37.26), 119 (39.77), 91 (36.8), 77 (18.6) and 51 (5.01).

(3)

Results and Discussion

The ions located at m/z 399, 161 and 121 arise from characteristic fragmentation pattern expected of a chalcone. But the appearance of ions at m/z 296 and 134 with higher intensities shows greater degree of isomerisation of the chalcone 2 to the flavanone⁴. Compound 3 shows the molecular ion at m/z 430 with higher intensity (72.18) than that for compound 2. It ejects methoxyl radical easily as evident from the peak at m/z 399 which happens to be the base peak too. The ions appearing at m/z 296, 265 and 134 arise from the isomerised flavanone.

From the above spectral characteristics, it is clear that the two isomers can be distinguished only from the mass fragmentation data. The base peaks of 2 and 3 appear at m/z 134 and 399, respectively which are suggestive of the fact that the isomerisation, of the chalcone to the flavanone is much faster in 2 than in 3. The loss of the methoxyl group from the molecular ion to give the base peak at m/z 399 in 3 indicates the steric hindrance to isomerisation to flavanone. Hence, 3 must have the methoxyl group in 2-position in the B-ring and 2 will have the methoxyl group in 4-position.

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Biflavones from *Picea morinda* Linn.

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PICEA *morinda* Linn. (Syn. *P. smithiana*, Boiss; Fam.: Pinaceae) is a genus of tall evergreen trees, commonly known as *Spruce*, distributed in a temperate and cooler region of the Northern hemisphere

from the Arctic Circle to the high mountains of warm temperate regions¹. Literature survey showed that no work has been reported on this plant.

Experimental

The leaves of *Picea morinda* (1 kg) collected from Dehra-Dun, were extracted with hot ethanol and ethanolic concentrate was left in a refrigerator, when a greenish solid mass settled (5 g). It was filtered and washed with petroleum ether, benzene and chloroform. The purified yellow product gave positive tests for flavonoids and showed two brown spots on tlc (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36:9:5)² corresponding to R_f values of amentoflavone and its monomethyl ether. These were separated by preparative tlc (silica gel G) and labelled as PM (2 g) and PMI (4 mg) in order of increasing R_f values.

PMI, m.p. 218-19° was the minor component and characterised as 5,7-dihydroxyflavone by uv studies, λ_{max} (MeOH) 268, 334 nm + AlCl₃, 275, 384 (sh) nm + NaOAc 284, 338. It gave usual flavonoidic tests.

The chromatographically homogeneous fraction PM on methylation [(CH₃)₂SO₄-K₂CO₃] and tlc examination was found to be a mixture of three biflavones. These were separated by tlc (B-P-F), crystallised from CHCl₃, labelled as PMA, PMB, and PMC, and identified as hexa-*O*-methyl ethers of amentoflavone³, cupressuflavone⁴ and agathisflavone⁵, respectively. PM on acetylation with Ac₂O-Py, followed by fractional crystallisation with CHCl₃-MeOH gave two compounds, characterised as hexa-*O*-acetates of amentoflavone and cupressuflavone, respectively. The structures of all compounds were established by comparing the ¹H nmr data of their methyl ethers and acetates with those of authentic samples. However, the third component could not be purified by fractional crystallisations but presumed to be agathisflavone hexaacetate.

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Free Amino Acids of *Melastoma melabathricum*

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MELASTOMA melabathricum Linn.¹ (*Melastomataceae*) is a shrub of variable heights from 3 to 8 ft with bright pinkish flowers in the hilly areas as well as in the lower level lands of Tripura, Assam and Bangladesh. The leaves, flowers and fruits can be eaten. The plant is said to be useful in cholera, diarrhoea, prolonged fever, dysentery, leucorrhoea, healing wounds, skin diseases and for the preparation of gargles². Previous investigations revealed the presence of a purple dyestuff, β -sitosterol and melastomic acid (triterpene) in the roots^{2,3}, and aliphatic compounds in the aerial parts⁴ of the plant. To find out the diet value of the leaves in respect to amino acid content, we investigated chemically the leaves of the plant and isolated eleven amino acids among which five being essential. In the present communication, we report the isolation, identification and relative occurrence of these amino acids in leaves.

The leaves of the plant, *M. melabathricum* L. were collected from the tilla areas of Agartala in May, 1984. The air-dried leaves (500 g) were milled and extracted in a Soxhlet with petrol (b.p. 60-80°) and 90% ethanol successively for 48 h each. The alcoholic extract was concentrated and decolourised by refluxing with activated charcoal. The brown filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to a gummy residue (19.2 g). The residue (1 g) was demineralised in the usual procedure^{5,6} by passing through a column of Amberlite IR 120 (H). The column was washed with water (70 ml) till the eluate gave negative test with Molisch reagent for carbohydrates. The amino acids were then eluted with 5% NH₄OH solution. The elution was continued till a drop of eluate failed to give bluish violet colouration on a filter paper moistened with ninhydrin reagent (0.20% in acetone). The total eluate was concentrated under reduced pressure and paper chromatographed in descending technique on Whatman No. 1 in two directions⁷ using solvent system n-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O (12:3:5; solvent I) in one direction and PhOH-H₂O-NH₄OH (5:1.25:0.9; solvent II) in the other direction. Amino acids were located on chromatogram by spraying ninhydrin reagent and heating the paper at 100° for a few minutes. R_f values of amino acids were measured and compared with those of authentic samples. The amino acids were then identified as glycine, valine, leucine, isoleucine, methionine, tyrosine, hydroxyproline aspartic acid and glutamic acid by co-pc with authentic samples.